

IMPACCT: An Integrated Assessment Model for Policy and Financial Decision-Making in Energy Planning

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ABSTRACT

As global environmental challenges increase, the need for integrated energy modelling to facilitate data-driven decision-making in energy policy and finance is critical. However, most existing integrated frameworks are limited in their applicability, granularity, and accessibility, risking the exclusion of developing countries from the global energy transition. Social dimensions are also often insufficiently addressed, and financial planning is not integrated, leaving gaps between technical analysis, social considerations, and actionable investment pathways. To address this, the article presents the Integrated Model for Policy, Actions and Collaborative Climate Transitions (IMPACCT), a new comprehensive framework that soft-links seven significant open-source tools—MAED; OnSSET; OSeMOSYS, including CLEWs and SIBs; FlexTool; PathCalc; MINFin; and FINPLAN—for the first time. IMPACCT estimates energy demands from the electrified and unelectrified populations and calibrates the least-cost capacity mix to meet demands while taking into account land availability, water use, carbon emissions, and social factors. The capacity mix is further refined to ensure power system flexibility, and the technical outputs are visualised in an engaging interface. Financial strategies at national and utility levels complete the framework, supporting the practical realisation of the technical plans. By outlining a new process with open-source, user-friendly interfaces, this paper increases accessibility and ease of use, supports capacity building in developing countries, and facilitates collaboration across institutions and disciplines. It delivers a significant leap in energy modelling, social inclusion, and financial planning, advancing a more integrated approach to sustainable development. Overall, IMPACCT enables more transparent and collaborative decision-making, accelerating financial mobilisation for a just energy transition.

1. Introduction

Open-source data and energy modelling tools for evidence-based policymaking allow transparency, adaptability, and collaboration—all of which can accelerate the release of concessionary finance for sustainable development [1–8]. Multiple energy transition studies have incorporated these aspects; however, they typically utilise a single energy model rather than multiple [7, 9]. Single-model analyses usually cannot perform such extensive assessments to include considerations regarding energy demand and supply, power flexibility, land availability, water use, social factors, carbon emissions, financial strategies, and financial returns. Thus, they fail to provide a comprehensive representation of the factors that drive energy system development (i.e., macroeconomics affecting demand, investment profitability, and others) or the critical considerations for planning (i.e., job creation, resource use, and other implications).

Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) have been developed to address these challenges by combining insights from multiple sectors to inform energy planning, climate policy, and sustainable development [10, 11]. These models

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have gained prominence through their inclusion in assessments by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and the International Energy Agency's World Energy Outlook [12]. To date, several well-established IAMs exist; however, as we show in Section 2, all of these models remain inaccessible to a broader audience and often fail to adequately incorporate the social and financial dimensions essential for a just energy transition [13–15]. This highlights a significant gap in the availability of open-source, user-friendly integrated energy modelling approaches that go beyond purely technological analyses to integrate social and financial considerations. Additionally, rather than developing yet another standalone modelling tool to address these gaps, we argue in this paper that a more effective approach is to create a framework that connects a suite of specialized, well-established models—each excelling in its respective domain—while providing methodologies for their integration and execution [14, 16–19].

This article bridges the gap by conceptualising the Integrated Model for Policy, Actions, and Collaborative Climate Transitions (IMPACCT)—a framework soft-linking seven significant and widely-used open-source energy modelling tools for the first time, with potential to expand further. By integrating a suite of existing open-source and user-friendly tools, IMPACCT lowers the barriers to entry for those without coding skills or advanced computational resources, enabling a broader range of users to engage in energy and financial modelling. Unlike all existing integrated assessment models (IAMs), IMPACCT explicitly incorporates social and financial dimensions, enabling users to move from technical analysis and social considerations to actionable investment strategies. Its modular approach allows decision-makers to apply models they are already familiar with while fostering interdisciplinary collaboration. Along with open data, capacity-building, and stakeholder and community engagement, IMPACCT aims to deliver insights and be utilised by policymakers, analysts, and researchers within energy modelling, policy, and finance, for a just, equitable, and orderly energy transition.

IMPACCT also provides flexibility in the scope of analysis. Users can choose between a variety of analyses: (1) translating techno-economic plans into financial actions at the national and utility levels through a unidirectional pipeline; (2) refining case studies through feedback loops between two tools; or (3) combining both approaches. To aid readability, this paper demonstrates the framework primarily as a unidirectional pipeline, guiding users from energy demand forecasting to identifying financially viable utility-level projects that meet the estimated demand. Nevertheless, feedback loops are also highlighted throughout to illustrate how users can refine analyses and assumptions.

The modelling tools in the framework are chosen for their open-source code, user-interface accessibility, significance and wide use, and their differing aspects of the energy transition. The tools, their descriptions, inputs, and outputs are provided in Table 1. Their linkages in IMPACCT are illustrated in Figure 1.

The paper is organised as follows: Section 2 reviews existing IAMs and identifies critical gaps, while Section 3 details the seven tools in IMPACCT and implemented linkages between them. Section 4 covers the conceptualisation and methodology of IMPACCT, followed by Section 5, which discusses the benefits, limitations, initial uptake, and future directions of IMPACCT. Finally, Section 6 presents the conclusions.

2. A Review of Integrated Assessment Models and Frameworks

Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) are multidisciplinary tools that combine information from multiple sectors to support energy planning, climate policy, and sustainable development [10, 11]. IAMs emerged in response to the limitations of traditional sectoral models, which struggled to capture cross-sectoral linkages [38, 39]. By integrating representations of energy systems, economic development, land use, climate change, and other sectors, IAMs enable users to explore long-term interdependencies and trade-offs across a wide range of socio-economic, technological, and environmental drivers.

IAMs comprise a family of models and frameworks, each with distinct methodologies tailored to answer specific questions. IAMs operate across multiple spatial scales—global, regional, and national—and typically assess pathways over long-term horizons, often extending to 2050, 2100, or beyond. They have been widely applied in scientific literature [40], international policy assessments [13], and government legislation [41], supporting evidence-based decision-making processes [14]. Over the past few decades, IAMs have played a crucial role in shaping global climate and energy policy, particularly through their inclusion in assessments by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate

Table 1

List of the seven open-source tools in IMPACCT, their developers, brief description, key inputs and modelled outputs.

Name	Developer	Description	Key inputs	Key outputs
MAED Model for Analysis of Energy Demand	International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA)	Simulates future energy demand based on a set of assumptions on medium- to long-term demographic, socioeconomic, and technological developments [20, 21]	Population growth, economic development, sectoral energy intensities, technological efficiency improvements, and lifestyle and consumption patterns	Detailed estimates of useful energy demand and hourly electricity demand, disaggregated by end-use category for the industry, transport, services, and housing sectors
OnSSET Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool	KTH Royal Institute of Technology (KTH)	Optimises the medium- to long-term expansion of electricity access, incorporating geospatial factors such as energy demand, infrastructure constraints and regional distribution [22, 23]	Population distribution, existing electrification rates, infrastructure proximity, renewable resource availability, and technology costs	Estimates of current un-electrified residential demand supplied by off-grid technologies, their associated capacity factors, and network distribution costs
OSeMOSYS Open Source Energy Modelling System	KTH Royal Institute of Technology (KTH)	Optimises the least-cost capacity expansion plan to meet a pre-defined demand in the medium- to long-term [24, 25]. This can be expanded to include the Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems (CLEWs) [26, 27] and Social Impacts and Benefits (SIBs) approaches [28, 29]	Energy demand estimates, technology costs and efficiencies, system operation parameters, fuel prices, and resource availability	Least-cost capacity expansion plan broken down into capital, fixed, and variable costs, and its associated emissions, land and water use, and social implications
FlexTool	International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA)	Optimises least-cost power system flexibility assessments for one year based on national capacity investment plans and forecasts [30, 31]	Electricity demand profiles, generation capacity and technology mix, transmission infrastructure, flexibility constraints, and storage options	Identification and quantification of flexibility indicators (curtailment, loss of load, reserve adequacy), as well as least-cost dispatch solutions
PathCalc Pathways Calculator	Loughborough University & Imperial College London	Optimises thousands of medium- to long-term scenarios from a 'base' OSeMOSYS model, leveraging ambition levels and levers to show the impact of various choices on key metrics such as investments and emissions [32, 33]	Quantified targets and policies within a nation, as well as a 'base' OSeMOSYS model	Interactive visualization dashboard with thousands of potential least-cost capacity expansion plans and their associated costs and emissions
MINFin Model for Informed National Financing	University of Oxford & Imperial College London	Simulates strategies to bridge financing gaps in energy sector transition plans by comparing financing requirements with projected cash flows and quantifying the shortfalls [34, 35]	Long-term capacity expansion investment plan, including fixed and fuel costs, the associated carbon emissions, and historical financing data	Annual financing repayment needed to service debt and equity in support of the long-term energy plan
FINPLAN Model for Financial Analysis of Electric Sector Expansion Plans	International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA)	Simulates the financial performance of power plant projects over their lifetime by comparing the cost components with available financing sources [36, 37]	Market conditions, investment, fixed, and fuel costs, financing structure, electricity tariffs, and project lifetime	Overall project profitability, including electricity generation costs, cash flow estimates, financial performance indicators, tariff requirements, and revenue forecasts

Change (IPCC) and the International Energy Agency's World Energy Outlook [12].

- ① OSeMOSYS uses energy demand forecasts for the electrified population from MAED to calculate the least-cost capacity mix
- ② OSeMOSYS uses energy demand forecasts for unelectrified populations from OnSSET to calculate the least-cost capacity mix, with electricity price from OSeMOSYS refining OnSSET results
- ③ FlexTool uses the capacity mix from OSeMOSYS to assess power flexibility, refining OSeMOSYS results with alternate expansion plans
- ④ FlexTool uses projected hourly electricity demand profiles from MAED to assess power flexibility
- ⑤ CLEWs and SIBs can be incorporated in OSeMOSYS to assess the energy-land-water nexus and social impacts
- ⑥ PathCalc uses an OSeMOSYS ‘base’ input file, generating thousands of interactive scenarios to refine insights through levers and ambition levels
- ⑦ MINFin uses cost requirements suggested by OSeMOSYS to develop a national financing strategy, which can, in turn, be used as constraints within OSeMOSYS
- ⑧ FINPLAN uses techno-economic requirements from OSeMOSYS to assess the financial viability of utility-level power plants, which can, in turn, be used as constraints within OSeMOSYS
- ⑨ FINPLAN uses MINFin financing terms to assess power plant viability, and revenues from FINPLAN can refine MINFin results

Figure 1: Infographic displaying how the seven open-source tools: MAED, OnSSET, OSeMOSYS, FlexTool, PathCalc, MINFin, and FINPLAN, can be utilised together for IMPACCT and support wider understanding of energy systems modelling. Solid arrows depict a one-way input-output link in the direction of the arrow, while dashed lines represent feedback loops within the tools connected by the bidirectional arrow. This paper highlights the unidirectional pipeline from techno-economic modelling to financial planning in order to release concessionary finance for sustainable development; however, the flexibility of IMPACCT also allows users to utilise the feedback loops to refine certain models or sectors based on specific interests or needs.

The most widely used IAMs include AIM-Hub (Asia-Pacific Integrated Model), GCAM (Global Change Assessment Model), IMAGE (Integrated Model to Assess the Global Environment), MESSAGE-GLOBIOM (Model for Energy Supply Strategy Alternatives and their General Environmental Impact linked with the Global Biosphere Management Model), REMIND-MAGPIE (Regionalized Model of Investments and Development combined with the Model of Agricultural Production and its Impact on the Environment), and WITCH (World Induced Technical Change Hybrid model) [13, 40–42]. Nonetheless, the IAM community continues to expand in response to growing demand and evolving policy needs, both through the development of new models and the refinement of existing frameworks.

Table 2 summarises IAMs recognised by the Integrated Assessment Modelling Consortium (IAMC) [43]. To ensure transparency, the list is limited to IAMs for which complete documentation is publicly available. The models are compared based on equilibrium type, modelling approach, sectoral coverage, open-source status, reliance on open-source platforms and/or solvers, and user-accessibility. A model is deemed user accessible if its use does not require programming skills, proprietary software licenses, or high-performance computing resources, all of which are common barriers to access for researchers in developing countries.

The comparison shows that IAMs vary widely in their structure, scope, and methodological approaches. One key distinction in structure is between general and partial equilibrium modelling. General equilibrium models, such as MESSAGE-GLOBIOM, capture economy-wide interactions and market feedbacks, making them suitable for analysing the broader economic impacts of climate policies across sectors, households, and trade. Partial equilibrium models, such as IMAGE and TIAM-UCL, focus on detailed representations of specific sectors like energy or land use without modelling the entire economy's feedback effects. Some IAMs, such as REMIND-MAGPIE, combine both approaches. REMIND employs a general equilibrium approach to model global energy and economic interactions, while MAGPIE uses a partial equilibrium framework to provide detailed insights into agricultural production, land use, and food markets.

Analytical approaches also vary. Some IAMs, such as WITCH, cost-optimize pathways subject to climate and energy constraints. Others, such as AIM-Hub and GCAM, simulate plausible system evolution based on behavioural assumptions, historical trends, and policy inputs. A few IAMs combine both optimisation and simulation approaches. For instance, COFFEE-TEA allows users to optimise a least-cost pathway through COFFEE and explore its income effects and macroeconomic feedback through TEA.

Furthermore, IAMs vary in sectoral coverage. Some focus on energy systems and emissions, enabling users to understand how energy transitions influence greenhouse gas emissions. Others have expanded to include additional resource systems, such as land use and water availability, and their interdependencies across the energy-land-water nexus. These integrated frameworks enable the assessment of cross-sectoral trade-offs, such as the impacts of water constraints on energy production, or bioenergy production on food security and forest conservation.

Table 2: List of fully documented IAMs recognised by the IAMC, their developers, type of equilibrium, modelling approach, open-sourceness, and user accessibility. Note that this list is limited to those with complete, publicly available documentation to ensure transparency. All information is from the IAMC [43]. IMPACCT is listed at the bottom of the table for comparison.

IAM	Developer	Type of equilibrium	Modelling approach	Sectors	Open-source code	Open-source platform and/or solver	User accessible
AIM-Hub	National Institute for Environmental Studies & Kyoto University (Japan)	General	Simulation	Economy, energy, land, emissions	No	No	No
BLUES	Cenergia (Brazil)	General	Optimisation	Energy, land, emissions	No	No	No
C3IAM	Beijing Institute of Technology (China)	General	Optimisation	Energy, land, emissions, climate	No	No	No
COFFEE-TEA	Cenergia (Brazil)	General & partial	Optimisation & simulation	Energy, land, emissions	No	No	No
DNE21+	Research Institute of Innovative Technology for the Earth (Japan)	Partial	Optimisation	Energy, land, emissions	No	No	No
GCAM	Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (USA)	Partial	Simulation	Energy, land, water, emissions, climate	Yes	Yes	No
GEM-E3	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (Greece)	General	Optimisation	Energy, emissions	No	No	No
GRACE	Centre for International Climate Research (Norway)	General	Simulation	Energy, emissions	No	No	No
IFs	Pardee Centre (USA)	General	Simulation	Energy, land, water, emissions, climate, social	No	Yes	Yes
IMACLIM	Centre International de Recherche sur l'Environnement et le Développement & Société de Mathématiques Appliquées et Sciences Humaines (France)	General	Simulation	Energy, land, climate	No	Yes	No
IMAGE	PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency (Netherlands)	Partial	Simulation	Energy, land, water, emissions, climate	No	No	No
MESSAGE-GLOBIOM	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (Austria)	General	Optimisation	Energy, land, water, emissions, climate	No	No	No

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IAM	Developer	Type of equilibrium	Modelling approach	Sectors	Open-source code	Open-source platform and/or solver	User accessible
POLES	European Commission (Belgium)	Partial	Simulation	Energy, land, emissions	No	No	No
PROMETHEUS	E3Modelling (Greece)	Partial	Simulation	Energy, emissions, climate	No	No	No
REMIND-MAgPIE	Potsdam Institut für Klimafolgenforschung (Germany)	General & partial	Optimisation & simulation	Energy, land, emissions, climate	Yes	No	No
TIAM-UCL	University College London (UK)	Partial	Optimisation	Energy, emissions, climate	No	No	No
WITCH	European Institute on Economics and the Environment (Italy)	General	Optimisation	Energy, land, water, emissions, climate	No	No	No
WITNESS	Linux Foundation & Open-Source for Climate (n/a)	General	Optimization & simulation	Energy, materials, population, environment	Yes	Yes	No
IMPACCT	Loughborough University, Imperial College London, Technical University of Munich & University of Oxford	Partial	Optimisation & simulation	Energy, land, water, emissions, climate, social, finance	Yes	Yes	Yes

2.1. Critical Gaps in Integrated Assessment Models

While many IAMs exist (Table 2), none offer an open-source, user-friendly framework that explicitly integrates the social and financial dimensions critical for energy transition analysis. This limits the Global South's capacity to conduct cross-sectoral studies, where accessible tools are essential for researchers without advanced computing skills. Most IAMs already fail to capture key differences in developing regions, resulting in misrepresented energy transition pathways [42]. It also hinders stakeholder engagement, despite governments increasingly prioritising social outcomes in energy planning [8, 14, 19]. Financial feasibility is another overlooked barrier, with many IAMs failing to assess whether technically optimal plans are economically viable [44]. The following subsections examine these gaps in detail, highlighting why accessible, socially responsive, and financially informed modelling approaches are urgently needed for a just global energy transition.

2.1.1. Lack of Transparency

Table 2 shows that most IAMs remain closed with expensive proprietary software. Of the 18 IAMs reviewed, only two are fully open-source, with freely available code and compatibility with open solvers like Mathprog or Python. The remaining models either restrict access to their code or rely on expensive proprietary platforms and solvers such as GAMS and CPLEX, creating significant financial and technical barriers for broader participation [5, 24]. Despite advances in modelling techniques, transparency in model development and application has received comparatively little attention [3, 14, 18, 45, 46].

Transparency is critical for ensuring models are scientifically credible and useful to policymakers [2, 4–6, 8, 14]. Without open access, hidden assumptions, simplifications, or coding errors are impossible for external users to detect, undermining trust in the results [45]. Open-source models, by contrast, allow others to reproduce findings, verify results, and subject the code to rigorous scrutiny, helping to minimise human error and improve reliability [3, 5, 24, 46]. Beyond transparency, open models foster collaboration and avoid duplication of effort, reducing the risk of fragmented, low-quality modelling efforts [5]. Open-source communities enable diverse contributors, such as academics, government analysts, and others, to improve models collaboratively and strengthen the link between modelling and policy development [3, 7].

Ultimately, open-source models lower entry barriers, widen participation, and encourage innovation [13]. Publicly available code is also more likely to be reused, adapted, and supported by an active user community [3, 4]. Although some developers are cautious about open-sourcing their models due to concerns over intellectual property misuse or user support burdens [3, 4, 18, 45], others, like DeCarolis et al. [45], argue that "the benefits of model transparency outweigh these legitimate concerns". Cao et al. [46] further reiterates this, noting "transparency is even more important than technical skills".

2.1.2. Lack of User-friendliness

Table 2 shows that only one IAM is user-friendly. While some IAMs have been made open-source, most remain inaccessible to non-experts due to steep learning curves and the absence of intuitive interfaces. This limits their adoption in developing countries, where ease of use and local capacity building are critical for sustainable energy transitions. Many developing countries face limited institutional capacity, scarce technical expertise, and constrained computing resources [47–50], making it difficult to engage with complex and highly technical models.

User-friendly interfaces and participatory modelling approaches can help overcome these barriers. By simplifying the modelling process, they enable a wider range of users, including policymakers and non-technical stakeholders, to engage meaningfully in energy planning. This engagement builds trust, improves understanding, and increases acceptance of energy decisions, all of which are critical for successful policy implementation and investor confidence [8, 14, 51]. However, without accessible tools, many stakeholders are excluded from the dialogue, and some policymakers remain sceptical of modelling's value for decision-making [51].

Capacity building is key to changing this dynamic. It requires long-term investment in local skills development rather than continued reliance on external experts [18, 52–54]. Accessible, open-source models with low technical barriers allow local users to learn by doing, gradually developing a skilled pool of experts who can maintain and apply these tools in their own context. Without such efforts, developing countries risk being left out of the global energy

transition, leaving billions of people out of the energy transition dialogue [54]. Therefore, improving usability and strengthening local capacities are critical steps toward more inclusive, sustainable energy transitions.

2.1.3. Lack of Social Drivers and Implications

Table 2 shows only one IAM that includes both social drivers and implications. In recent years, IAMs have been criticised for being overly techno-centric, focusing primarily on cost-optimal pathways while neglecting the social dimensions of energy transitions [13, 16, 18, 19, 55]. This limits their usefulness to policymakers seeking to design energy transitions that are just and equitable [56]. Research has shown that incorporating social factors improves both the performance of models [57] and the relevance of their results [19].

Socio-economic aspects are generally only included in supply-demand models. Most models rely solely on GDP as the primary socio-economic driver for estimating energy demand, but this approach can produce inaccurate assessments by leaving out the complexities of human behaviour and economic dynamics [17]. Important social and behavioural drivers, such as household decisions to install efficient lighting or shifts in transport modes, are often overlooked, leaving a gap in understanding how user choices impact energy demand [42, 56]. There is also a growing consensus that models should incorporate a broader range of economic sectors and activities to reflect demand more accurately [13]. For example, the industrial sector, which is hard to decarbonise, requires a deeper analysis of how user demand, material flows, and energy consumption interact to shape future electricity demand [58]. Poor representation of these socio-economic drivers can lead to misleading policy insights. Thus, to design effective policies, it is essential to account for the underlying human drivers of demand [14].

Many IAMs also overlook the interaction between the energy system and society at large, missing key impacts on people's lives and livelihoods. Factoring in social considerations, such as employment and health outcomes, can help reveal the distributional effects of energy transitions, especially on low-income and underrepresented communities [19]. By identifying these impacts, policymakers can better ensure that energy transitions are inclusive and equitable. These social considerations can also inform trade-offs tailored to specific development priorities. Additionally, highlighting social factors can make energy plans more attractive to financiers and increase the likelihood of securing support [59]. For example, Costa Rica's National Decarbonisation Plan, launched in 2019, was developed with multi-sectoral stakeholder input and long-term modelling that considered poverty reduction, job creation, and air quality. This inclusive approach helped mobilise US \$2.4 billion in concessionary finance to support the plan's implementation [8]. Integrating social dimensions is therefore critical to generating actionable insights for a sustainable and just energy transition.

2.1.4. Lack of Financial Markets and Mechanisms

Table 2 highlights that IAMs currently do not incorporate financial planning. While IAMs excel at techno-economic optimisation and long-term mitigation analysis, they rarely include detailed representations of financial markets or financing mechanisms. As a result, they fail to reflect real-world constraints such as capital availability, financial risk, and investor behaviour, leading to misestimations of the true costs of the energy transition [13, 15, 60, 61].

Sanders et al. [15] notes that "there have not been attempts to explicitly link finance [...] to transition investments by technology". Models usually overlook key aspects of project financing, such as the balance between equity and debt, distinctions between public and private capital, and the role of interest rates—all of which are essential to the implementation of energy projects as they can influence the pace of the energy transition [61]. There is also limited analysis of how financial structures evolve over time and the financial structuring of projects, such as the use of balance sheet financing, where projects are funded directly by companies, or project finance, where standalone project entities are created. [15]. Keppo et al. [13] further argues that IAMs could be strengthened by incorporating detailed financing schemes, debt budgeting, and the dynamic interaction between debt accumulation and interest rates.

Addressing these gaps is increasingly important. A lack of available finance could slow or stall the energy transition, and this concern has begun to receive attention from policymakers, central banks, and the broader financial community [13]. Incorporating financial market dynamics into IAMs would make their results more robust and relevant for policy and investment planning. Furthermore, such improvements would enable the exploration of how green

monetary policies—such as green bonds, favourable interest rates, or sustainable investment mandates—could support sustainable energy transitions.

3. Open-Source Energy Planning and Financial Modelling

3.1. Energy Planning and Financial Modelling Tools

There has been a growing recognition in recent years of the importance of open-source software, emphasising collaborative modification, use, and distribution of source code to the public [3–7]. This trend is evident in the fields of energy modelling and financial planning, where the focus on transparency, collaboration, and accessibility within communities is fundamental in driving impactful changes towards sustainable development [8, 62]. Thus, this analysis focuses on seven open-source and user-friendly tools that align with the U4RIA goals (ubuntu, retrievability, repeatability, reconstructability, interoperability, and auditability) [63] to ensure that the models remain accessible to a broad community of researchers, consultants, and policymakers. The following subsections provide a concise overview of each tool's methodology, as well as its applications.

3.1.1. Model for Analysis of Energy Demand (MAED)

MAED is a bottom-up tool that evaluates future energy demand and hourly electricity demands [20, 21]. The tool has two components: (1) MAED-D and (2) MAED-EL. MAED-D forecasts future energy demand in a country or region by considering medium- to long-term scenarios involving socio-economic, technological, and demographic development. The tool connects the specific energy demand for producing various goods and services identified in the model to the corresponding social, economic, and technological factors that influence this demand. The total energy demand for each end-use category is defined by four main sectors: industry (including agriculture, construction, mining, and manufacturing), transportation, service, and household.

The energy demand in each considered sector can also be disaggregated into a large number of sector-specific end-uses, such as urban households' demand, intracity passenger transport demand, manufacturing demand, and more. Each end-use category corresponds to a given service or the production of a certain good, with the nature and level of the demand for these services and goods being driven by several determining factors, including demographic and macroeconomic growth, number of electrical appliances used in households, peoples' preferences for transportation modes, national priorities for the development of specific industries or economic sectors, and so on.

MAED-EL, on the other hand, converts the forecasted electricity demand for each of the aforementioned sectors to the hourly electricity demand for a chosen year. Several factors influence the calculation of the hourly demand profiles, including the trend of the average electricity demand growth rate during the year (which can be obtained from MAED-D), the electricity consumption changes due to the various seasons in a year (i.e., winter, summer, etc.), the type of day (i.e., working, weekends, holidays, etc.), and the hourly variation of electricity consumption during the day. The MAED tool utilises a static modelling approach, which may not capture the dynamic nature of energy systems and the interactions between different sectors and stakeholders. Nonetheless, the model is one of a suite of tools used extensively for sustainable energy planning through manuals, training, and e-learning sessions [64].

3.1.2. Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET)

OnSSET is a tool designed for spatial electrification planning in regions with limited access to electricity [22, 23]. The software uses geographic information systems technology and data on infrastructural parameters, population distribution, and energy resource availability to develop scenarios that optimise the spatial distribution of electricity expansion to meet residential and small-scale commercial electricity demand. Examining the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE), the geospatial tool identifies the cost-optimal split between centralised grid extensions, mini-grids, and stand-alone technologies to meet future electricity demand, which is pre-determined by population growth and electrification rates. However, OnSSET does not consider the on-grid power generation split, instead modelling all grid-connected generation as a single technology. Nonetheless, the open-source geospatial tool has been utilised by world-leading institutions such as The World Bank [65]. To further enhance accessibility, the tool has online self-learning material and is taught in numerous capacity-building events around the globe [64].

3.1.3. *Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS)*

OSeMOSYS is an energy systems planning tool where medium- to long-term energy system models are generated to identify the least-cost capacity expansion plan to meet a pre-defined energy demand within the boundaries of a set energy system (e.g., country, region, or sector) [24, 25]. The tool's open-code and 'blocks of functionality' structure (i.e., the modular components that perform the required tasks in OSeMOSYS) has often been relatively straightforward to customise. The tool is utilised not only for its energy capacity and financial planning capabilities but for its expansion opportunities, which includes the addition of smart grids [66], the energy-land-water nexus via the *Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems (CLEWS)* approach [26, 27], and *Social Impacts and Benefits (SIBs)* [28, 29].

In more detail, the CLEWs approach is used to analyse the interconnections between climate, land, energy, and water systems, ensuring resource efficiency. As it utilises the same optimisation code as OSeMOSYS, integrating CLEWs will influence the energy capacity expansion plan based on resource availability, competition, and system-wide constraints. For example, the expansion of hydropower capacity in an energy model could be limited if water availability decreases due to agricultural demand or climate-induced droughts, helping policymakers to avoid overestimating renewable energy potential [67]. By capturing these cross-sector dynamics, CLEWs supports more sustainable and resilient development pathways, particularly in resource-constrained or climate-vulnerable regions.

The SIBs approach, on the other hand, follows an input-output methodology and serves as an analytical framework rather than an optimisation model. Thus, SIBs does not directly affect the capacity expansion plan but provides valuable insights into key social indicators, supporting efforts to protect and uplift marginalised communities—an area of growing importance for policymakers. For example, the framework was applied to Costa Rica's National Decarbonisation Plan, launched in 2019, where it helped integrate considerations such as poverty reduction, job creation, and air quality. This inclusive approach contributed to mobilising US \$2.4 billion in concessionary finance to implement the plan [8]. It is essential to note that both CLEWs and SIBs are not modelling tools themselves; they are only approaches which can be incorporated in any capacity expansion model, such as the OSeMOSYS modelling tool.

Although it lacks built-in stochastic modelling and detailed spatial resolution, OSeMOSYS' accessibility and versatility with the CLEWs and SIBs approaches has positioned itself as a top-performing open source tool [7] used by national governments, the United Nations, and research academics for policy development and financial planning [4]. It is also an educational tool to generate energy-land-water models within numerous global higher education institutions worldwide, such as Addis Ababa University (Ethiopia), University of Brasilia (Brazil), University of Gadjah Mada (India), and Loughborough University (UK) [68, 69]. Online resources for self-learning are freely available, and capacity-building events utilising the tool are well-known [64, 68–70].

3.1.4. *FlexTool*

FlexTool is an energy system optimisation tool which analyses the operational aspects of a full power system based on a planned energy capacity expansion [30, 31]. The tool performs detailed single-year flexibility analyses to identify potential underlying flexibility bottlenecks and evaluate possible flexibility options, such as the deployment of electricity storage, implementation of demand response, and addition of sector-coupling technologies such as power-to-heat, electric vehicles and hydrogen production through electrolysis. Alongside these, the tool provides a least-cost optimisation of the generation mix. However, FlexTool is limited to single-year analyses and therefore cannot model how the power system's capacity evolves over a long period. Instead, users have to identify individual years (e.g., 2030, 2040, or 2050) to model on FlexTool. Nonetheless, FlexTool has been used to examine national plans by various scholars [71–73]. To improve accessibility, FlexTool offers freely accessible online self-learning resources and is being included in various capacity-building events worldwide [64, 70].

3.1.5. *Pathways Calculator (PathCalc)*

PathCalc is an interactive web-based tool for visualising thousands of potential energy and emissions pathways using a 'base' OSeMOSYS model, i.e., an OSeMOSYS model with the basic input data (e.g., technology costs, efficiencies, etc.) but minimal constraints (e.g., no limits on electricity imports, no minimum solar use, etc.). These relaxed constraints allow PathCalc flexibility when generating thousands of scenarios based on certain ambition levels and levers, quantifying how different strategies impact key metrics such as emissions and costs. [32, 33].

By translating complex modelling results into intuitive and engaging visualisations, PathCalc facilitates engagement between technical experts, policymakers, stakeholders, and the public, ensuring diverse perspectives are considered in energy transition discussions. PathCalc is based on the 2050 Calculator concept, where users view scenarios by selecting ambition levels for each of the tool's levers [74]. Levers are areas of action for reducing emissions, such as behaviour change or deployment of specific technologies. Each lever has four ambition levels ranging from 'no effort' to 'maximal effort', and ambition level definitions are based on expert and stakeholder judgement. While the 2050 Calculators are accounting models which run in real-time on the web tool and include over 40 levers, the PathCalc web tool displays pre-run cost-optimised OSeMOSYS scenarios and can include up to 6 levers in its first iteration. At the time of writing, PathCalc is actively being applied and tested in regional contexts such as Viet Nam and Laos [32].

3.1.6. Model for Informed National Financing (MINFin)

MINFin is an analytical model designed to examine financing gaps and develop affordable strategies at the national level [34, 35]. Its overarching aim is to facilitate collaboration between energy and finance ministries, thereby ensuring the integration of macroeconomic and financial factors into national energy planning processes. The tool is structured around three essential input pillars: investment needs, financing baseline, and funding baseline. Within the first pillar, investment needs, the annual capital investment required to implement specific plans or policies for sustainable development, is calibrated. Secondly, in the financing sources, the country's historical experience in financing energy projects, including the types of financiers involved and the financing terms available, is examined. The funding baselines pillar then identifies the resources within the country's energy sector that can be utilised to service debt and fund projects. If the funding baseline does not meet the financing requirements, the plan is considered unaffordable, resulting in the identification of a financing gap. At the time of writing, MINFin is gaining traction and being trialled within academia and ministerial planning [34].

3.1.7. Model for Financial Analysis of Electric Sector Expansion Plans (FINPLAN)

FINPLAN is an accounting model that assesses the financial viability of plans and projects [36, 37], taking into account different financial and technical sources such as foreign exchange rates, investment costs, loan parameters, plant size, electricity generation, and so on. Using this information, FINPLAN computes the projected cash flows, financial ratios, shareholders' returns, including the net present value (NPV) and internal rate of return (IRR), and other financial indicators. FINPLAN also supports different financial structures, including both balance sheet and project financing. Unlike other tools, where various energy technologies can be assessed, FINPLAN can only model the financial outcomes of one power plant or a group of power plants with the same technology type. Nonetheless, FINPLAN has been used for financial planning capacity building through manuals, training, and e-learning sessions [64].

3.2. Existing Cross-Cutting Analyses

While studies have explored the capabilities of isolated open-source modelling tools [65, 71, 75, 76], a limited amount of literature has actually investigated their integration potential. From a range of tools, the linkage of OnSSET and OSeMOSYS has been widely studied and peer-reviewed [77–79]. Although all focus on Africa, the approach to linking the two tools is similar, whereby the current un-electrified residential demand supplied by off-grid technologies, capacity factors of such off-grid technologies, and the network distribution costs from OnSSET can be fed into OSeMOSYS. A feedback loop can further be established by utilising the electricity price generated from OSeMOSYS and integrating it back into OnSSET.

Another link that has been analysed is OSeMOSYS and FlexTool [80, 81]. In these two peer-reviewed studies, FlexTool validated OSeMOSYS' least-cost expansion scenarios by analysing the power system flexibility trade-offs associated with persistent plant availability issues. The process involved selecting the capacity mix derived from the OSeMOSYS model for a specific year and integrating it into FlexTool. A feedback loop between OSeMOSYS and FlexTool can also be developed by reintegrating the newly optimised capacity mix for that chosen year from FlexTool back into OSeMOSYS. Lastly, the MAED and OSeMOSYS integration has also been investigated by one peer-reviewed paper [82]. In this analysis, MAED is initially used to predict future electricity demands for the industry, service, administrative, residential, and agriculture sectors. Subsequently, these useful energy demands are fed into OSeMOSYS to optimise a least-cost capacity expansion plan to fulfil the demands. In contrast to the previously

Table 3

Summary of existing modelling analyses on open-source tools integration.

OnSSET & OSeMOSYS		
Year	Author(s)	Title
2017	Moksnes, N. et al. [77]	Electrification pathways for Kenya—linking spatial electrification analysis and medium to long term energy planning
2021	Pappis, I. et al. [78]	Influence of Electrification Pathways in the Electricity Sector of Ethiopia—Policy Implications Linking Spatial Electrification Analysis and Medium to Long-Term Energy Planning
2022	Pappis, I. [79]	Strategic low-cost energy investment opportunities and challenges towards achieving universal electricity access (SDG7) in forty-eight African nations
OSeMOSYS & FlexTool		
Year	Authors	Title
2024	Borba, B. et al. [80]	Integrated Long-Term Expansion Planning and Short-Term Operation Assessment for Decarbonisation Pathways in Brazil Considering Utility-Scale Storage
2024	Kihara, M. et al. [81]	Mid- to long-term capacity planning for a reliable power system in Kenya
MAED & OSeMOSYS		
Year	Authors	Title
2024	Slimani, J. et al. [82]	Towards a sustainable energy future: Modelling Morocco's transition to renewable power with enhanced OSeMOSYS model

mentioned integrations, the MAED-OSeMOSYS link operates without a feedback loop.

Nonetheless, each study notes that combining bottom-up approach tools offers a more comprehensive approach to energy planning and sustainable development. By integrating multiple methodologies, decision-makers can also gain enhanced insights into the broader aspects of energy resources, infrastructure requirements, and potential challenges. Table 3 summarises currently available integration analyses on the selected open-source tools, as mentioned above. Presently, there is a lack of analyses exploring the expansion of the above tool integrations to include elements like open-source financial planning tools and socio-political factors [19]. These existing analyses offer insights that are techno-economically focused, leaving a gap in financial and socio-political modelling for the mobilisation of funds for sustainable development.

4. The IMPACCT Framework

As mentioned in Section 1, IMPACCT bridges techno-economic and financial planning tools, enabling an evidence-based approach to developing financially feasible power expansion plans that can attract concessional finance. Rather than building a single, all-encompassing model from scratch, IMPACCT adopts an assemblage approach, soft-linking existing, well-established partial equilibrium models. This approach has several advantages: it better represents the complexity of energy systems, reduces the time, cost, and effort required for model development, and leverages the familiarity users already have with these tools—an important factor influencing tool adoption in practice [14].

The structure of this section guides the user through a unidirectional pipeline, progressing from techno-economic modelling to financial assessment and planning, whilst highlighting potential feedback loops throughout the pipeline. The unidirectional pipeline concludes when each utility-level project analysed in FINPLAN is deemed financially feasible. However, the framework can be flexible, based on user needs and interests. For instance, if the primary focus is on energy access, users may emphasise the OnSSET-OSeMOSYS link and refine results through a feedback loop without going through the unidirectional pipeline and integrating financial planning tools. Alternatively, if financial feasibility is a key consideration alongside energy access, MINFin and/or FINPLAN can be integrated after the model refinement process to assess the viability of an energy access plan.

Following Figure 1, IMPACCT starts with MAED and OnSSET. MAED investigates the forecasted hourly electricity demand profile and the future energy demand of the currently electrified grid, while OnSSET computes

the future demand of the unelectrified grid. These outputs serve as predefined inputs for OSeMOSYS, where the most cost-effective capacity expansion plan to meet the energy demands is developed. A feedback loop may be further developed between OSeMOSYS and OnSSET, allowing the electricity price output from OSeMOSYS to refine the geo-spatial analysis. Along with the proposed hourly electricity demand profile from MAED, FlexTool then assesses the flexibility of the OSeMOSYS-designed power system and provides insights about potential operational bottlenecks in the power system, such as loss of load and renewable generation curtailment. Furthermore, FlexTool can also identify potential solutions for the flexibility problems identified. Depending on the FlexTool results, a loop between OSeMOSYS and FlexTool can be developed to refine the power system design based on the information obtained by the flexibility analysis. Similarly, the results from this new OSeMOSYS study can be used to further improve OnSSET results.

Next, the CLEWs approach may be introduced to expand one's OSeMOSYS analysis to include interlinkages between the climate, land, energy, and water. Simultaneously, the SIBs approach can be utilised to understand social implications, such as job creation, global warming costs, and pollution, from a proposed capacity expansion plan. For engagement purposes within academia, government, or other institutions, a 'base' OSeMOSYS input file can also be used to visualise thousands of potential pathways via interactive ambition levers and levels on PathCalc. This, in turn, enhances and refines the insights from OSeMOSYS, enabling more nuanced decision-making. Bringing in financial aspects, MINFin can be utilised to create a national financial strategy based on investment needs calculated by OSeMOSYS. Lastly, cost outputs from OSeMOSYS and loan parameters from MINFin can also be used to evaluate financial returns such as revenues, internal rate of return, and debt repayment time of power plants on FINPLAN. Depending on MINFin and FINPLAN results, feedback loops can be created with OSeMOSYS to further refine the capacity expansion plan based on national-level and project-level financial feasibility. A feedback loop can also be created between FINPLAN and MINFin, where revenue outputs from the former can be integrated into the funding baseline of the latter.

IMPACCT can be categorised into five sub-frameworks based on user needs or interests: (1) techno-economic; (2) energy-land-water nexus; (3) social and environmental; (4) visualisation; and (5) financial, as illustrated in Figure 2. Details on the methodology of the interlinkages are noted in the following subsections, with the techno-economic sub-framework in Section 4.1, energy-land-water in Section 4.2, social and environmental in Section 4.3, visualization in Section 4.4, and financial in Section 4.5. To further support users, Section A.1 outlines the inputs and outputs for each tool linkage, including data formats and units, while Section A.2 provides step-by-step hands-on exercises. Together, these resources promote transparency and make IMPACCT easier to follow and apply in practice.

4.1. Techno-Economic Sub-Framework

The techno-economic sub-framework is the starting point of IMPACCT and includes four tools: MAED, OnSSET, OSeMOSYS, and FlexTool. Figure 3 lists the key outputs and inputs essential for this particular sub-framework.

4.1.1. MAED to OSeMOSYS

Firstly, MAED-D is used to forecast annual energy demands of the industrial, transport, household, and services sectors, factoring in assumptions related to socioeconomic, technological and demographic changes. Following this, the average electricity demand growth rate for a chosen year, as calculated by MAED-D, can be fed into MAED-EL to derive the hourly electricity demand profiles for the aforementioned economic sectors. MAED can therefore generate two variables: (1) the estimated useful energy demand for each sector by end-use (i.e., manufacturing motive power demand, passenger rail demand, household cooking demand, etc.), and (2) the accompanying hourly demand profile for the electricity end-use demand for each sector (i.e., cooling demand, electric appliances demand, etc.). Thus, two steps exist to translate MAED's energy demand estimates into OSeMOSYS. From MAED-D, all *useful energy demand* by end-use, except the useful electricity end-use demand, shall be directly taken and placed in OSeMOSYS as an *accumulated annual demand* for the respective sectoral end-use - a relatively straightforward process. As the remaining estimated useful electricity demand from MAED-D has an accompanying *electricity demand profile* from MAED-EL, the user shall place the MAED-D annual demand in OSeMOSYS' *specified annual demand* and the MAED-EL hourly demand in OSeMOSYS' *specified demand profile* instead. Note that the hourly time resolution as calculated from MAED-EL can also be further harmonised into smaller time slices for computational ease with OSeMOSYS. A time slice is a distribution of the OSeMOSYS modelling period (typically a year) into smaller segments that represent

Figure 2: Infographic displaying IMPACCT segregated into five sub-frameworks: (a) Techno-economic; (b) Energy-land-water nexus; (c) Social and environmental; (d) Visualisation; and (e) Financial.

Figure 3: Key outputs and inputs needed for the techno-economic sub-framework of IMPACCT, consisting of OnSSET, MAED, OSeMOSYS, and FlexTool.

different time intervals. This method has been shown to lose little information [83]. For example, 8,760 hours, as shown on MAED-EL, can be retrofitted to fit with OSeMOSYS’ 96 (or 16, or 8) time slices. Care should also be taken so that the *accumulated annual demand* is not defined for a commodity if its *specified annual demand* for the same year is already defined and vice versa.

Additionally, the OSeMOSYS model will require a reference energy system that mirrors the MAED system. A reference energy system represents the activities and relationships within an energy system, including the estimated energy demands, energy conversion technologies, fuel mixes, and the resources required to meet those demands. A

similar reference energy system for both tools is crucial to ensure seamless integration between the tools. To assist users in creating the necessary reference energy system for linking the tools, including technologies and commodities, Table 5 provides links to example reference energy system diagrams for the industrial, transport, household, and services sectors that one can adopt, adapt, and apply. It is also important to highlight that connecting a simulation tool like MAED with an optimisation tool like OSeMOSYS requires careful consideration to preserve the qualities of both tools. For example, if the user wishes to provide the ‘technology’ activity mix for each end-use demand (e.g., electric car, gasoline car, coal cooking, gas lighting, etc.) as it may be calculated from MAED-D, a sensible ‘buffer’ of around 20% above and below the estimated MAED-D ‘technology’ activity mix will allow OSeMOSYS flexibility in calibrating a least-cost model while still acknowledging MAED-D results. This can be done using the OSeMOSYS parameters *total technology annual activity upper limit* and *total technology annual activity lower limit*. Figures 6 to 10 detail the necessary outputs from MAED to integrate with OSeMOSYS. Additionally, a step-by-step exercise on integrating both tools can be accessed via Table 4.

4.1.2. OnSSET to OSeMOSYS (feedback loop)

OnSSET can be run simultaneously alongside MAED, obtaining the currently unelectrified off-grid demand estimates for the housing, services, agriculture, education, and healthcare sectors. These demands can be incorporated into OSeMOSYS as pre-defined demands. However, note that when combining these two tools, the geospatial aspect of OnSSET will be lost. Nonetheless, OSeMOSYS is a model that can be used at different disaggregation levels. Thus, this challenge may be solved by creating multiple OSeMOSYS models at a village or regional level and stitching these multiple OSeMOSYS models together for a national analysis. Similar to the MAED-OSeMOSYS integration, the total off-grid demand can be placed in the *specified annual demand* parameter if there is an accompanying *specified electricity demand profile* for off-grid users; otherwise, the *accumulated annual demand* should be used. Note that all outputs from OnSSET are presented by a five-year ‘snapshot’ period; thus, the user must divide the results by 5 to get annual values. There is therefore a limitation in this method; however, the duration of the ‘snapshot’ period is sufficiently small to offer a reasonably acceptable representation of off-grid demand.

The reference energy system within OSeMOSYS must also mirror the system in OnSSET, incorporating off-grid technologies such as stand-alone diesel, hydropower minigrad, hybrid solar PV minigrads, etc. To assist users in creating the necessary reference energy system for linking the two tools, Table 5 provides a link to an example reference energy system diagram for the off-grid system that one can adopt, adapt, and apply. If the user wishes to disaggregate the total off-grid demand by technology activity, a sensible ‘buffer’ of around 20% above and below the estimated OnSSET technology activity mix will allow OSeMOSYS further flexibility in calibrating a least-cost model. This can be done using the OSeMOSYS parameters *total technology annual activity upper limit* and *total technology annual activity lower limit*. Besides the demand, capacity factors and renewable potential for off-grid technologies can also be obtained from OnSSET and inputted into OSeMOSYS. Lastly, the network distribution costs can be calculated from OnSSET and used as the capital costs for the transmission and distribution systems within OSeMOSYS. Throughout the integration process, the user must ensure unit consistency between the two tools and divide OnSSET results by 5 to obtain annual values.

Additionally, a feedback loop between OnSSET and OSeMOSYS can be established, where the average electricity price from OSeMOSYS can be calculated and fed back into OnSSET. This updated grid electricity cost inputted into OnSSET will impact the off- to on-grid cost optimisation process. To fully calibrate the two models, the process of integrating OnSSET to OSeMOSYS and vice versa should be repeated until there is a convergence of results, i.e., until the LCOE produced between two iterations of OnSSET runs has a difference of less than 10% [84]. Figures 11 and 12 detail the necessary outputs from OnSSET for integrating with OSeMOSYS, and vice versa. In-depth hands-on exercises for the OnSSET-OSeMOSYS and OSeMOSYS-OnSSET links can also be accessed via Table 4.

4.1.3. OSeMOSYS to FlexTool (feedback loop)

FlexTool conducts a single-year flexibility analysis, including detecting possible flexibility constraints within the power system. Hence, in an integrated analysis between OSeMOSYS and FlexTool, OSeMOSYS provides the cost-optimal capacity expansion plan of the power system in the future, and FlexTool evaluates the proposed system from

an operational perspective. One important aspect the user has to consider when performing an integrated OSeMOSYS-FlexTool analysis is that the modelling approach of the two tools for the power sectors is different. OSeMOSYS models the power sector connected to the rest of the energy system. Therefore, electricity is modelled as a demand commodity consumed in end-use sectors and supplied by power plants. Alternatively, FlexTool deploys a more detailed and topological power-based approach. Thus, the electricity system is modelled as a node (or multiple nodes interconnected with transmission lines), where the power supply technologies and the electricity demand are located. Moreover, FlexTool accounts for power system operational characteristics (e.g., inertia, reserve provision, etc.) and additional detailed technology options not included in OSeMOSYS (e.g., electricity interconnections, demand response, etc.). Ultimately, the two tools differ in terms of temporal resolution. OSeMOSYS is used for long-term multi-year and multi-resource analyses, and each year is modelled with some sampled representative timeslices. FlexTool, on the other hand, focuses on a single year, which is modelled with a full hourly resolution.

From a technical point of view, the OSeMOSYS implementation shall precede the FlexTool analysis. The FlexTool model can be partially set up based on the inputs and outputs of the OSeMOSYS model. The key parameters transferred from the OSeMOSYS inputs to FlexTool are the annual electricity demand and the techno-economic characteristics of the power technologies. From OSeMOSYS outputs, the key parameter needed for populating FlexTool inputs is the capacity of the power generators and electricity storage units. Additionally, if the OSeMOSYS analysis affects the final electricity demand, this parameter shall be sourced from the OSeMOSYS results. For example, if OSeMOSYS decides whether and to what extent electric vehicles are utilised to satisfy transport activity demand, the amount of electricity consumed by electric vehicles shall be sourced from OSeMOSYS outputs. The transfer of input and output parameters of OSeMOSYS to FlexTool is illustrated in Figure 13. Table 4 also provides a link to a step-by-step exercise on integrating the two tools.

It should be noted that a series of parameters necessary for FlexTool cannot be sourced directly from OSeMOSYS. FlexTool provides a more detailed representation of power technologies and thus requires additional technology characteristics compared to OSeMOSYS. Typical examples are the so-called flexibility parameters of power-generating units, such as ramping capabilities and minimum stable load, among others. Such parameters need to be sourced from the international literature. Additionally, since the temporal resolution is different, parameters expressed in a time series format, like the demand profile and the capacity factor profiles of renewable energy plants, cannot be directly transferred from OSeMOSYS' input file to FlexTool. Nevertheless, the hourly demand profile for the chosen year can be obtained from MAED-EL (see Section 4.1.4). Furthermore, it is important to ensure that the full time series of capacity factors of power plants used in FlexTool match the ones used to produce the representative reduced time slices in OSeMOSYS.

If a FlexTool analysis highlights issues with the power system flexibility, one can delve into two solutions. If concerns such as curtailment or loss of load are present in the analysis, the user can: (1) integrate different flexibility options such as electric vehicles, battery storage, power-to-heat, power-to-hydrogen, and demand response. Nonetheless, data regarding these technologies will be required for this sector-coupling analysis; (2) run FlexTool in 'investment mode', where an alternative capacity expansion plan can be analysed. This can then be integrated as parameters in OSeMOSYS. Similar to the OnSSET-OSeMOSYS integration, a feedback loop may also be explored with OSeMOSYS and FlexTool, where a convergence of results is needed to fully calibrate the two models [84].

4.1.4. MAED to Flextool

As mentioned in Section 4.1.1, MAED-D calculates the average electricity demand growth rate for a chosen year, which can be fed into MAED-EL to derive the hourly electricity demand profiles for the industrial, transport, household, and services sectors. MAED-EL, therefore, generates the hourly demand profile for the electricity end-use demand for each sector. As FlexTool requires the hourly demand profile for one year to carry out the power flexibility assessment, the hourly electricity demand profile from MAED for a selected year can be directly inserted into the FlexTool. However, it should be noted that a typical FlexTool model combines the hourly demand profiles of the industrial, residential, and services sectors in a single profile, while treating transport separately—effectively modelling two different 'grids' in FlexTool. The segregation is due to the electrified transport demand behaving differently from other sectors. While industrial, residential, and service loads are typically inflexible and follow predictable daily patterns, transport demand can be more dynamic, with charging loads that can be shifted based on grid conditions or user preferences. Additionally, some transport modes can provide demand-side flexibility through managed charging or

vehicle-to-grid interactions, which can also be modelled on FlexTool. Despite this, linking MAED and FlexTool is still straightforward, where the industrial, residential, and services hourly demand profiles from MAED are summed into a single profile, while the transport sector hourly demand profile can be used directly in FlexTool. The MAED-FlexTool link is illustrated in Figure 13, and a detailed step-by-step guide on this is accessible via Table 4.

4.2. Energy-Land-Water Sub-Framework

The energy-land-water sub-framework extends the energy-related foundation laid by OSeMOSYS, offering an integrated, nexus-based framework encompassing energy, water, land, and climate systems via the CLEWs approach. This symbiotic relationship allows for a comprehensive exploration of resource systems through the lens of nexus thinking. By adopting a nexus approach, CLEWs transcends sectoral silos to recognise that these energy and earth systems are deeply interconnected and interdependent [27, 69].

For example, energy production often requires significant water use, particularly in thermal power plants that rely on water for cooling. More water-intensive energy sources can strain water supplies, impacting availability for other uses. At the same time, water production also depends on energy inputs for pumping water from surface and groundwater sources for irrigation, thermal power plant cooling, desalination, and public water supply. Similarly, land plays a crucial role in the energy-water nexus. The allocation of land for energy production, such as growing biofuel crops or constructing solar and wind farms, competes with food production and natural ecosystems. Poor practices like excessive fertiliser use on energy crops can also pollute waterways, and deforestation for biofuels impacts the climate through lost carbon sequestration. Simultaneously, energy is needed for land management, such as powering agricultural equipment for crop cultivation or facilitating land-use changes. Additionally, land use significantly affects water resources, as agricultural activities influence water quality through nutrient runoff, pesticide contamination, and deforestation, which can reduce groundwater recharge. Finally, land use is deeply tied to climate, as agricultural expansion contributes to deforestation and methane emissions from livestock, whereas sustainable land management practices, including cover crops, reduced tillage, and wetland restoration, can help mitigate climate change.

For CLEWs to operate within OSeMOSYS, they must abide by the same modelling principles and have a predefined demand. Regarding the land component, this requirement comes in the form of a land use demand. For example, every type of land use represented in the model, i.e., tree cover, inland water, built-up land, etc., will require a representative demand. Typically, CLEWs models also incorporate arable land, which is 'governed' by a demand for the specific crops represented in the model. Additional complexity can also be added in the form of low-input arable land (i.e., rainfed crops) and high-input arable land (i.e., irrigated crops). Similarly, demand is also required for water and can be represented in terms of accumulated industrial, residential, commercial and agricultural demands. Thus, integrating CLEWs will influence the energy capacity expansion plan based on resource availability, competition, and system-wide constraints. Ramos et al. [85] provides an example reference energy system named 'RCLEWs' that one can modify and incorporate into OSeMOSYS for a CLEWs analysis. A hands-on methodology on further expanding an OSeMOSYS model to include the CLEWs approach is also accessible via Table 4.

4.3. Social and Environmental Sub-Framework

The social and environmental sub-framework extends the OSeMOSYS techno-economic approach to include social and environmental impacts and benefits that are directly affected by the energy sector. Recognising the growing importance of integrating social and environmental factors into energy systems modelling for value-driven insights, as emphasised by Dioha et al. [19] and Pfenninger et al. [16], this sub-framework incorporates the SIBs approach to quantify socio-economic variables. Initially, three aspects have been analysed for this sub-framework: (1) job generation, (2) air pollution, and (3) socio-environmental costs stemming from global warming.

Firstly, the energy transition offers substantial job creation opportunities, with clean technologies exhibiting high employment rates per installed capacity [86]. Since 2019, there has been a notable increase in the workforce within the energy sector, mainly driven by the rising prominence of clean energy. This shift has resulted in clean energy surpassing fossil fuels in terms of employment [87]. Using OSeMOSYS, the potential job creation through construction and manufacturing (C&M) can be assessed by incorporating coefficients that represent the number of C&M jobs produced for each added unit of installed capacity per technology [88]. Similarly, the operation and maintenance (O&M) jobs created can be modelled by utilising coefficients that represent the number of O&M jobs produced for each unit of

total installed capacity throughout the technology lifetime [88]. Both of these actions would involve creating 'dummy' C&M and O&M commodities and technologies on OSeMOSYS, which are then linked to the parameters *input to new capacity ratio* and *total capacity ratio*. A hands-on practice about the modelling approach is accessible via Table 4, and can be extended further to consider indirect employment [89, 90].

Secondly, the combustion of fossil fuels, particularly coal, results in outdoor air pollution, including fine particulates, sulfur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), and low-lying ozone. Natural gas combustion produces moderate amounts of NO_x. Gasoline and diesel combustion can yield SO₂, NO_x, volatile organic compounds (VOCs), and fine particulates, with emission rates influenced by vehicle regulations and fuel quality. Collectively, fossil fuel-related air pollution is estimated to cause 4.5 million premature deaths annually [91]. By employing estimated externality coefficients within OSeMOSYS, we can estimate the costs related to mortality and morbidity for individuals exposed to elevated concentrations of fine particulates in outdoor environments. This approach involves identifying and calculating the national air pollution cost [91], creating additional emission types within OSeMOSYS, updating the *emission activity ratio*, and defining the *emissions penalty*. A hands-on guide about the modelling approach is accessible via Table 4.

Thirdly, the costs of socio-environmental issues are rising due to extreme climate variations caused by global warming [91]. These expenses materialise in diverse outcomes affecting communities, such as crop loss, damage to infrastructure due to flooding, forest fires, water scarcity, and other related impacts. Previous studies have assessed these externalities using OSeMOSYS [28, 29]. This process is similar to the above, whereby the global warming cost by country and fuel is first identified and calculated [91], then creating additional emission types within OSeMOSYS, updating the *emission activity ratio*, and defining the *emissions penalty*. A hands-on guide about the modelling approach is accessible via Table 4.

While these methods allow a quick quantification of social and environmental implications and benefits using a straightforward multiplier methodology with annual coefficients, there is potential for more profound, complex analyses. Additional research has been conducted to extend the use of OSeMOSYS as a tool for assessing socio-economic variables. For instance, soft-linking with macroeconomic models can yield insights into the economy-energy nexus and the impact of emission reduction on economic growth [92]. Moreover, ad-hoc models can be linked to OSeMOSYS to assess fiscal impacts and distributional effects associated with decarbonization measures among selected stakeholders [93]. Examples like these will be studied to propose additional applications of the SIBs approach.

4.4. Visualisation Sub-framework

The visualisation sub-framework requires a 'base' OSeMOSYS input model—one with input data but minimal constraints—to allow PathCalc flexibility when generating thousands of OSeMOSYS scenarios. The results are displayed in PathCalc's interactive web-based tool. The visualisation sub-framework contains three key steps. The first two steps are done using the Excel-based 'PathCalc Planner'. Firstly, users select the levers to include in the web tool from a catalogue in the Planner, which is based on existing 2050 Calculators. Up to six levers can be chosen, each of which can be comprised of several sub-levers. The levers' ambition levels are then defined. Ideally, these draw on stakeholder consultations but may also be assumptions. By default, the lowest level of ambition ('no effort') aligns with the OSeMOSYS 'base' file scenario. Using the OSeMOSYS 'base' file in combination with lever data, the Planner generates thousands of OSeMOSYS input files for each combination of lever and ambition level. Lastly, the thousands of OSeMOSYS input files are run using a script, and results are visualised on the web tool using the PathCalc visualisation code. By visualising thousands of interactive, optimised scenarios, users can explore the different optimal pathways to enhance and refine the insights from OSeMOSYS, thereby creating a feedback loop and enabling more nuanced decision-making. A step-by-step guide on integrating OSeMOSYS and PathCalc, including links to prototypes of the PathCalc Planner and modelling script, is accessible via Table 4.

4.5. Financial Sub-framework

The financial sub-framework forms the latter part of IMPACCT and includes three tools: OSeMOSYS, MINFin, and FINPLAN. Figure 4 lists the key outputs and inputs needed for this part of IMPACCT.

Figure 4: Key outputs and inputs needed for the financial sub-framework of IMPACCT, consisting of OSeMOSYS, MINFin, and FINPLAN.

4.5.1. OSeMOSYS to MINFin (feedback loop)

MINFin is a model designed to examine and develop financing strategies for energy pathways at the national level. The model, therefore, complements OSeMOSYS by translating the techno-economic capacity expansion plan into a coherent financing strategy. The model comprises three input pillars: investment needs, financing baseline, and funding baseline. Financial outputs from OSeMOSYS, such as capital investment and operating costs, serve as essential parameters for input into MINFin. Firstly, the capital investment forms the foundation for estimating future power plant investment needs in MINFin. The operation and maintenance costs, on the other hand, allow for a comparative assessment of fossil fuel expenses and potential savings between scenarios, adding to a country's funding baseline in MINFin. Emissions from OSeMOSYS can also be included in MINFin to showcase the environmental benefits of transitioning to a scenario such as Net-Zero, offering users a strong incentive to pursue more ambitious decarbonization strategies. Furthermore, an implicit cost of carbon can be applied to the carbon emissions associated with the expansion plan, which is of potential interest from a carbon market perspective.

A feedback loop with OSeMOSYS can further refine the capacity expansion plan. The cost of capital estimates from the financing baseling in MINFin can be integrated into OSeMOSYS as technology-specific discount rates, representing hurdle rates and influencing the merit order of technologies. Generally, if MINFin results indicate that the national financing strategy is unachievable, adjusting OSeMOSYS to set less ambitious climate targets can delay the surge in financing requirements and ensure a more feasible investment trajectory, preventing financial bottlenecks. The key parameters to create an OSeMOSYS-MINFin integration are illustrated in Figures 14 and 15. A hands-on exercise for integrating OSeMOSYS and MINFin is accessible via Table 4. However, note that additional financial parameters are needed for a complete MINFin analysis. This includes historic lending volumes and terms of finance, information on sector cashflows, government budgets and international grants, which can be gathered from open-access online databases.

4.5.2. OSeMOSYS to FINPLAN (feedback loop)

After developing a national capacity expansion plan, the next step often involves assessing the financial feasibility of a particular power plant over its operational lifetime. Thus, FINPLAN can be integrated into the framework after OSeMOSYS. This integration enables a comprehensive understanding of the complexities regarding shareholders' return, cash inflow and outflow, financial ratios, and others, in sustaining the financial viability of power plants over time. As these financial parameters are specific to a singular power plant, or a group of power plants under one company, it is strongly suggested that one type of power plant, or a group of the same type of power plants constructed in the same year, as recommended by OSeMOSYS, be modelled on FINPLAN instead. If the user wishes to model the whole power system, it is advised to create multiple individual case studies that can be joined together externally. From OSeMOSYS, financial results such as capital investments, O&M costs, fuel costs, and electricity prices can be translated into

FINPLAN for the model to understand the costs associated with developing and running a power plant. Additionally, the capacity expansion volume and electricity production, as calculated from OSeMOSYS, can be brought into FINPLAN to define the size of the power plant(s). Depending on FINPLAN results, a feedback loop can be established with OSeMOSYS to further refine the capacity expansion plan based on project-level financial feasibility. For example, if FINPLAN indicates that the proposed projects are financially unviable, adjusting OSeMOSYS parameters to set less ambitious climate targets can ensure that new power plants operate without financial constraints. The key parameters to create an OSeMOSYS-FINPLAN integration are illustrated in Figure 16. A step-by-step guide on linking the tools together can also be accessed via Table 4.

4.5.3. MINFin to FINPLAN (feedback loop)

To capture the impacts of national financial conditions on power plants, loan parameters from MINFin can be inputted into FINPLAN. This includes the loan repayment structure (principal or principal+uniform repayment), average term of loan, and associated interest rate. Combining these data with other external data necessary for a FINPLAN analysis (exchange rates, inflation rates, construction time, proportion of international and national funding, etc.) will allow the user to identify the additional equity, debt, or subsidy needed from organisations for the power plant(s) to be financially operational throughout the modelling period. Further, the revenue calculated from FINPLAN can be incorporated back into MINFin's funding baseline to create a feedback loop. Revenue income is a crucial metric for assessing the financial performance and growth of a company. For instance, if a country anticipates high export revenues, this income can be included in the pool available for funding capital investments in domestic power projects. However, the cost of capital and financial structures in FINPLAN must align with those in MINFin when establishing the feedback loop. This is to ensure that inflows and outflows, including revenue streams, are consistently calibrated, preventing inconsistencies in financial estimates. The key parameters to create a FINPLAN-MINFin integration are illustrated in Figure 14. Hands-on exercises for the interactions of FINPLAN and MINFin are accessible via Table 4.

5. Discussions

5.1. Benefits and Innovations

IMPACCT is the first integrated assessment framework to combine open-source code, solvers, user-friendly interfaces, and comprehensive documentation. By improving accessibility compared to existing IAMs, it enables analysts in resource- and skills-constrained contexts, including marginalised communities and non-expert government officials, to undertake energy modelling and financial planning aligned with their energy transition goals [14, 24]. This supports capacity building and promotes inclusivity, allowing broader participation in energy policy and decision-making for a just and equitable transition.

Another advantage is that IMPACCT captures social drivers and implications, aspects which are often overlooked in current IAMs [17, 19]. In MAED, energy demand in all sectors is modelled with a bottom-up methodology by specifying socio-economic, technological, and demographic drivers—for instance, household size, appliance ownership, shifts in transport modes or improvements in industrial energy efficiency. SIBs complements this by quantifying social outcomes of technical energy transition plans, such as but not limited to job creation, global warming costs, and air quality, providing a social view of potential policy implications.

To the best of our knowledge, IMPACCT is the first IAM framework to explicitly embed financial planning. MINFin and FINPLAN enable users to explore financial market dynamics and project financing mechanisms into the future, including equity versus debt, public and private funding sources, and distinctions between balance sheet and project financing. This integration of financial analysis addresses an important gap identified in the IAM literature [13, 15], improving the finance lens of energy transition scenarios.

A key strength of IMPACCT is its integration of technical, social, and financial dimensions of energy transitions. It incorporates well-established tools that have been tested and documented by domain specialists, and it can adapt to diverse user needs, whether an in-depth analysis of specific processes (feedback loops) or broad system-wide assessments (pipeline assessment). For example, users interested in the integration of variable renewables can utilise OSeMOSYS and FlexTool in a feedback loop to evaluate operational impacts, while others who are interested in finance planning can link OSeMOSYS outputs to MINFin and FINPLAN only to assess the financial feasibility of

infrastructure investments.

Lastly, IMPACCT's broad sectoral coverage, accessibility, and collaborative design encourage cross-sectoral and cross-institutional dialogue. Government agencies, academic institutions, financial organisations, and other stakeholders often work in silos, each adopting their own modelling approaches [94]. IMPACCT encourages stakeholders to share data and modelling outputs to co-develop harmonised and credible energy transition plans. For instance, an energy ministry and finance ministry might jointly utilise the OSeMOSYS–MINFin–FINPLAN workflow to ensure technology pathways are financially viable. Similarly, an academic engineering department could collaborate with the energy ministry to refine an OnSSET–OSeMOSYS assessment. By explicitly linking sectoral analyses, IMPACCT can help to bridge sectoral silos, enable iterative model refinement and support the development of more collaborative, evidence-based policy outcomes.

5.2. Limitations and Complexities

The coupling of specialised models in IMPACCT introduces interoperability challenges, which currently require manual intervention to ensure consistency. For example, transferring technical and financial outputs from OSeMOSYS to FINPLAN requires careful conversion between units, such as from PJ to GWh. Similarly, adapting the hourly demand profiles from MAED to OSeMOSYS's 96-timeslice temporal structure requires additional data processing. Moving data from spatially detailed tools like OnSSET to the single-node structure of OSeMOSYS also results in a loss of spatial granularity; however, this can be partially addressed by running multiple village-scale OSeMOSYS models and aggregating the results. Nonetheless, these manual conversions for units, temporal, and spatial structure are documented, and step-by-step guidance is provided to the users (Table 4).

The unidirectional IMPACCT process can also be resource- and time-intensive. Integrating seven distinct tools requires significant effort to align data structures, assumptions, and outputs, demanding both labour and time. In many regions, key data such as energy demand, technology costs, or financial terms are scarce, outdated, or unofficial, introducing uncertainty into model results [17, 47]. Addressing these gaps requires not only technical fixes but also extensive stakeholder engagement to validate assumptions and improve data accuracy. Thus, capacity building, better institutional data-sharing, and targeted data collection are essential to ensure that IMPACCT informs decision-making in a meaningful and context-sensitive way, rather than reinforcing data limitations or systemic gaps.

Although IMPACCT addresses several gaps in the existing literature by integrating techno-economic, social, and financial dimensions, it does not yet cover all aspects of the energy transition. Key areas such as critical minerals supply chains, clean cooking solutions, and macroeconomic feedbacks between energy, investment, and growth remain outside the current framework. However, IMPACCT is designed to be modular and expandable, and future developments aim to incorporate these aspects through additional tools and models, as discussed in the following subsection.

Like all IAMs, IMPACCT simplifies the complexity of real-world systems. Combining multiple tools enhances the representation of energy, financial, and social dimensions, but each tool brings its own assumptions and limitations, as detailed in their respective references. No model can fully capture the dynamic, nonlinear, and interconnected nature of energy systems. Yet, abandoning IAMs is neither practical nor desirable—they remain essential for testing cost and performance assumptions and have been central to shaping global low-carbon transition scenarios [42]. Rather than viewing results as definitive answers, users should apply models to explore alternative pathways toward a shared vision of a sustainable energy future, as recommended by Sgouridis et al. [95].

5.3. Initial Uptake and Future Work of IMPACCT

At the time of writing, IMPACCT is being utilised by the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme's capacity-building initiative, which brings together participants from diverse institutions and government departments within a country. This approach enables different stakeholders to specialise in individual tools while working collaboratively to link them across sectors and disciplines [96]. Beyond national efforts, IMPACCT is also gaining traction among international organisations [97], as more actors seek to soft-link modelling tools for a wider understanding of energy transitions.

In terms of future work, IMPACCT will incorporate additional open-source tools for a broader coverage of the energy transition. However, it is critical to recognise that there are trade-offs and escalating complexities in integrating further modelling tools. Thus, selective consideration is needed to prioritise tools that offer the most value. A preliminary assessment identified nine potential tools that can be appended to IMPACCT, extending its coverage to include the data, cooking, transport, critical minerals, and life cycle assessment aspects, which are all crucial to facilitate energy systems planning. These tools are listed below. Figure 5 further displays the possible linkage of the tools within IMPACCT.

1. **Energy Access Explorer (EAE):** an online, interactive, geospatial platform developed by the World Resources Institute that enables users to identify high priority areas where energy access can be expanded [98]. Once these areas are identified, the user may carry out an in-depth analysis either on OnSSET or OnStove, ensuring efficient resource allocation.
2. **Open Source Spatial Clean Cooking Tool (OnStove):** a spatial tool developed by KTH comparing the relative potential of different cookstoves based on their costs and benefits [99]. The tool may interact with OnSSET to combine clean cooking and electricity access [100], as well as feed into OSeMOSYS to develop a capacity expansion plan for clean cooking.
3. **Energy Balance Studio (EBS):** a tool created by the IAEA that offers a systematic framework for organising energy statistics data. This ensures data consistency, accuracy, and comparability. The data can then be used as an input for energy planning models such as MAED.
4. **Open Source Mobility Model (OSeMobility):** currently under development by the University of Strathclyde, Oxford University, and Imperial College London, this modular transport systems modelling framework allows stakeholders to explore credible transport futures through a socio-technical approach [101]. The tool provides a direct interface with OSeMOSYS to enable quantification of transport futures on broader energy, emissions, and development goals.
5. **Mat-dp:** a model created by the University of Cambridge that computes the amount and type of materials required for constructing various systems or resource transformations, including those found along any supply chain. Nonetheless, it is mainly utilised to study the materials needed for constructing low-carbon systems and estimating the environmental implications associated with these materials [102]. This model can, therefore, expand an OSeMOSYS analysis to understand the materials required based on a capacity expansion plan.
6. **Multi-Regional Analysis of Regions through Input-Output (MARIO):** a framework developed by the Polytechnic University of Milan to model additional supply chains through a hybrid life cycle assessment approach at meso- and macro-scale [103]. This tool can be integrated with OSeMOSYS to analyse the supply chain effects of technological or policy interventions.
7. **Fossil Fuel Retirement Model (FFRM):** a tool originally constructed by The World Bank that enables the user to estimate the cost of compensating investors for early withdrawal of fossil fuel power plants [104]. This can serve as a continuation of a renewable energy capacity expansion plan proposed by OSeMOSYS. Additionally, results from this model, such as the present value of the foregone net revenues of stranded fossil fuel plants, can be fed into MINFin.
8. **Financing Costs for Renewables Estimator (FinCoRe):** a tool developed by Imperial College London that estimates the cost of capital for renewable energy power plants [105]. These capital costs can be fed into OSeMOSYS, FlexTool, MINFin, and FINPLAN to assess the least-cost capacity expansion plan and its financial feasibility.
9. **Climate Finance Tracker (FinTrack):** a tool created by Imperial College London, which identifies potential future concessional finance envelopes [106] and can influence the financial assessments and planning in MINFin and FINPLAN.

IMPACCT also currently integrates selected models that continue to evolve. As these underlying tools and models advance, IMPACCT will be updated accordingly to incorporate the latest improvements, maintaining its accuracy and relevance. Additionally, the current social and environmental analysis (Section 4.3) covers only a subset of aspects. Future versions will broaden this scope to include further dimensions such as the economy-energy nexus, income levels, affordability, livelihoods (including road safety), and gender equality.

A unidirectional script is in development to automate the integration of the IMPACCT tools, enabling streamlined techno-economic to financial planning assessments. The hard-linking will speed up analysis, reduce human error, and

Figure 5: Linking of additional tools including EAE, OnSTOVE, EBS, OSeMobility, Mat-dp, MARIO, FFRM, FinCoRe, and FinTrack. These tools are highlighted in grey. Solid arrows depict a one-way input-output link in the direction of the arrow, while dashed lines represent feedback loops within the tools connected by the bidirectional arrow.

support framework validation and uncertainty quantification. It will also enable advanced methods like robust decision making (RDM) to identify resilient energy transition pathways under deep uncertainty, which would be difficult to explore manually.

Lastly, to enhance transparency and build confidence in the workflow, a validation exercise of IMPACCT is ongoing. The authors are conducting a unidirectional analysis that systematically passes results and inputs through each tool. This validation process is to be published in a series of papers following this conceptualisation article and will reveal data transformations, assumptions, and intermediate outputs. By documenting the entire process, the authors aim to improve reproducibility, credibility, and transparency, responding to calls for higher standards in open science and model validation [46].

Overall, the urgent need for integrated and automated tools to support rapid and robust energy planning decisions underscores the timeliness of this publication. By detailing IMPACCT and its conceptualisation, this work makes a critical contribution at a pivotal moment for both researchers and policymakers, laying the groundwork for future developments.

6. Conclusions

IMPACCT is the first of its kind in soft-linking seven significant open-source and user accessible modelling tools to provide a comprehensive approach to integrated energy systems planning. It includes techno-economic, energy-land-water, social and environmental, visualisation, and financial aspects. This interdisciplinary integration bridges critical gaps in existing IAMs, particularly enhancing transparency, stakeholder accessibility, and inclusion of social and financial considerations—areas often overlooked in traditional modelling approaches. By doing so, IMPACCT supports more coordinated, evidence-based, and just decision-making processes essential for sustainable energy transitions.

IMPACCT’s flexible design also allows users to tailor their analysis to their specific needs and capacities. Whether applying the full unidirectional pipeline that integrates all seven tools, selectively using a subset of tools with feedback loops, or adopting any combination in between as outlined by the IMPACCT methodology in this paper, users can tailor the framework to fit their institutional context and analytical goals. To ensure robustness and build confidence among users, a comprehensive validation process is underway. The authors are preparing a series of forthcoming papers, organised by tool, that will document the framework’s input and output data as well as its validation. This transparent

approach will strengthen IMPACCT's credibility and offer practical guidance for its application across diverse contexts.

Nevertheless, it is important to recognise that while these actions, along with IMPACCT, support energy and financial planning, they are not individually sufficient to guide a nation through the entire transition from energy systems modelling to investment-ready plans. To fully realise a just and sustainable energy transition, additional measures such as increased open data licensing in the public sector, building institutional capacity, fostering stakeholder engagement, employing iterative robust decision-making analysis, and others, will be critical [8, 18].

Ethics Statements

Not applicable.

Declaration of Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that have or could be perceived to have influenced the work reported in this article.

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A. Appendix

A.1. IMPACCT Data Inputs and Outputs

This subsection provides visuals on data inputs and outputs relating to the integration of the seven tools noted in this paper for IMPACCT. This includes the integration of: MAED and OSeMOSYS (Figures 6 to 10), OnSSET and OSeMOSYS (Figures 11 and 12), OSeMOSYS and FlexTool (13), MAED and FlexTool (Figure 13), OSeMOSYS and MINFin (Figures 14 and 15), OSeMOSYS and FINPLAN (Figure 16), and MINFin and FINPLAN (Figures 14 and 16). Note that the figures only provide the unidirectional pipeline between two tools. For feedback loops, users should integrate two diagrams accordingly, e.g., Figures 11 and 12 for the OnSSET-OSeMOSYS feedback loop.

Figure 6: Inputs and outputs needed for a MAED-OSeMOSYS integration, focusing on the industry sector.

Figure 7: Inputs and outputs needed for a MAED-OSeMOSYS integration, focusing on the transport sector.

Figure 8: Inputs and outputs needed for a MAED-OSeMOSYS integration, focusing on the household/residential sector.

Figure 9: Inputs and outputs needed for a MAED-OSeMOSYS integration, focusing on the services sector.

Figure 10: A 20% 'buffer' above and below the estimated MAED-D 'technology' activity mix, using the Total Technology Annual Activity Upper Limit and Total Technology Annual Activity Lower Limit parameters. The useful thermal demand from biomass and coal heating within the services sector is used as an example. The 'buffer' is recommended to allow OSeMOSYS flexibility in calibrating a least-cost model while still acknowledging MAED-D results.

Figure 11: Inputs and outputs needed for an OnSSET-OSeMOSYS integration. An example ‘buffer’ of 20% is included to define the agriculture end-use demand by technology (stand-alone PV, mini-grid hydro). This ‘buffer’ will allow OSeMOSYS flexibility in calibrating a least-cost model while still acknowledging OnSSET results. Note: *** indicates that further data processing is required, i.e., in translating average, maximum, and minimum capacity factors to a capacity factor in time series.

Figure 12: Inputs and outputs needed for an OSeMOSYS-OnSSET integration.

Figure 13: Inputs and outputs needed for an OSeMOSYS-FlexTool and a MAED-FlexTool integration. Note: *** denotes that further data processing is required, i.e., in translating capacity factor in time series to an hourly resolution.

Figure 14: Inputs and outputs needed for an OSeMOSYS-MINFin and a FINPLAN-MINFin integration.

Figure 15: Inputs and outputs needed for a MINFin-OSeMOSYS integration. Note: WACC = weighted average cost of capital

Figure 16: Inputs and outputs needed for an OSeMOSYS-FINPLAN and a MINFin-FINPLAN integration. Note: P = principal; I = interest

Table 4

Links to IMPACCT hands-on exercises for model-to-model integration.

IMPACCT link	Hands-on exercises
MAED-OSeMOSYS	https://zenodo.org/records/10968586
OnSSET-OSeMOSYS	https://zenodo.org/records/10968590
OSeMOSYS-OnSSET	https://zenodo.org/records/10968591
OSeMOSYS-FlexTool	https://zenodo.org/records/10968592
MAED-FlexTool	https://zenodo.org/records/14927286
OSeMOSYS-CLEWs	https://zenodo.org/records/10598875
OSeMOSYS-SIBs	Job generation: https://zenodo.org/records/10955876 Global warming costs: https://zenodo.org/records/10955773 Air pollution costs: https://zenodo.org/records/10955912
OSeMOSYS-PathCalc	https://zenodo.org/records/13988059
OSeMOSYS-MINFin	https://zenodo.org/records/10949846
OSeMOSYS-FINPLAN	https://zenodo.org/records/10968598
MINFIN-FINPLAN	https://zenodo.org/records/10968601
FINPLAN-MINFIN	https://zenodo.org/records/10968603

Table 5

Links to example RES diagrams for the industrial, transport, household, and services sector, as well as off-grid integration, that one can adopt, adapt, and apply.

Sector/System	Link
Industrial	https://zenodo.org/records/10948821
Transport	https://zenodo.org/records/10948821
Residential	https://zenodo.org/records/10948778
Services	https://zenodo.org/records/10948798
Off-grid	https://zenodo.org/records/10948836

A.2. IMPACCT Hands-on Exercises and Extra Material

To aid the user in utilising IMPACCT, step-by-step hands-on exercises by the authors have been created. Table 4 lists the respective links for each IMPACCT tool-to-tool linkage, while Table 5 includes links to the industrial, transport, residential, services, and off-grid RES that users can adopt, adapt, and apply for their analyses. Note that the hands-on exercises only provide the unidirectional pipeline between two tools. For feedback loops, users should implement two hands-on exercises accordingly, e.g., the OnSSET-OSeMOSYS and OSeMOSYS-OnSSET hands-on exercises for the OnSSET-OSeMOSYS feedback loop.

A.3. Modelling Tools Resources

This subsection provides references and links to key resources of each modelling tool (Table 6). A community forum is also available for these tools at forum.u4ria.org. This Energy Modelling Community Discourse Forum is a hub for discussions, troubleshooting, event updates, and sharing the latest publications on open-source energy modelling tools and frameworks. Additionally, the CCG programme hosts the Energy Modelling Platforms (EMPs), a series of capacity-building events. These platforms train individuals in the Global South, equipping them with the skills to collect relevant data, conduct their analyses, and develop credible investment proposals for clean energy infrastructure projects. More information regarding the EMPs can be found at climatecompatiblegrowth.com/energy-modelling-platform.

Table 6
Additional information on modelling tools and their resources.

Tool	Methodology	Source code	User interface	Learning material
MAED	[20]	https://github.com/Model-for-Analysis-of-Energy-Demand/MAED-Code	https://forms.office.com/e/cpCks1aVmY	https://www.open.edu/openlearncreate/course/index.php?categoryid=528
OnSSET	[22]	[23]	https://electrifynow.energydata.info/	https://www.open.edu/openlearncreate/course/index.php?categoryid=528
OSeMOSYS	[24]	https://github.com/OSeMOSYS/OSeMOSYS	https://forms.office.com/e/cpCks1aVmY	https://www.open.edu/openlearncreate/course/index.php?categoryid=528
FlexTool	[30]	https://github.com/irena-flextool/flextool	[31]	https://www.open.edu/openlearncreate/course/index.php?categoryid=528
PathCalc	[32]	[33]	https://pathcalc.github.io/pathcalc-web/	Coming soon
MINFin	[34]	https://github.com/MINFinModel/MINFin-Excel	https://forms.office.com/e/cpCks1aVmY	https://www.open.edu/openlearncreate/course/index.php?categoryid=528
FINPLAN	[36]	https://github.com/FINPLAN-Model/FINPLAN-Code	https://forms.office.com/e/cpCks1aVmY	https://www.open.edu/openlearncreate/course/index.php?categoryid=528